

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

Deliverable 3.1 Defined ToBRFV-resistant tomato varieties

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Defined ToBRFV-resistant tomato varieties

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ToBRFV: Tomato brown rugose fruit virus

WU: Wageningen University

VC: Volcani Center.

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

ToBRFV belongs to the genus of tobamoviruses, having a host range containing tomato, pepper plants (with no *L* resistance allele) and some Solanaceae weeds. As all the tobamoviruses, ToBRFV is a mechanically transmitted seedborne virus. Infected tomato plants with ToBRFV show symptoms on the leaves, such as interveinal yellowing, mosaic patterns, shape abnormalities and necrosis, and on the fruits, such as discoloration, shape abnormalities and eventually necrosis. ToBRFV was detected in a cultivation of tomato hybrids carrying *Tm-2²* *R* gene, indicating the ineffectiveness of this gene against ToBRFV. After the first identification in Israel and in Jordan in 2014, ToBRFV has been reported in the recent years in Germany, Italy, the UK, Greece, the Netherlands, Spain, Turkey and Italy. In 2019 the virus was added to the EPPO alert list and emergency measures are currently in force in the EU. The severity of the disease caused by ToBRFV, the scarcity of available resistance genes, and the rapid spread of ToBRFV around the world make this virus a worldwide threat for tomato production.

Aiming to identify ToBRFV resistance in tomato wild relatives and to introgress them into tomato cultivars, WU has set up a disease assay at seedling stage to test tomato plants with ToBRFV. After screening about 60 accessions of 12 different *Solanum* species, two *S. pennellii* accessions have been identified resistant to ToBRFV.

In order to find ToBRFV-resistant rootstocks to prevent root mediated plant infections with ToBRFV, in VC we have screened 142 tomato plant accessions provided by Prof. Dani Zamir and NewBreed LTD. The tests were conducted by ToBRFV leaf inoculations of the tomato accessions analyzed phenotypically and by ELISA test using ToBRFV specific antibodies, which were raised against ToBRFV virions purified from *Tm-2²* resistant tomato plants. The efficiency of the rootstocks in hindering root mediated ToBRFV infection was tested under stringent conditions of truncated roots dipped in a ToBRFV inoculum before planting the grafted plants, which had scions of *Tm-2²* resistant tomato plants.

2 INTRODUCTION

Screening for natural resistance to tobamovirus

The new tobamovirus ToBRFV is currently posing a huge threat to tomato worldwide as it breaks natural *Tm-2*-based resistances in commercial tomato varieties. Pepper plants harboring no *L* resistance alleles are susceptible to ToBRFV infection as well. After the first identification in Israel and in Jordan in 2014, ToBRFV has been reported in the recent years in Germany, Italy, the UK, Greece, the Netherlands, Spain, Turkey and Italy. In 2019 the virus was added to the EPPO alert list and emergency measures are currently in force in the EU. The risk for a fast spread of ToBRFV in the north-western European, high-tech tomato greenhouses, is important, as shown by the very rapid spread in the Netherlands, where at least 300 to 400 hectares of tomato greenhouses were already affected in 2019. Tobamoviruses are seed borne viruses although seed to seedlings transmission is low. Infected seeds and plant debris may constitute a primary infection via soil and irrigation water contamination. The primary mode for tobamovirus contamination is mediated by mechanical plant manipulations and root injury.

In the WP3 of VIRTIGATION project, WU aims to screen in-house maintained wild tomato accessions for ToBRFV resistance and to introgress the identified resistance into cultivated tomato.

VC part was to screen tomato varieties for rootstock uses in order to prevent root mediated ToBRFV infection of *Tm-2²* resistant tomato plant scions. Resistant rootstocks are important for areas that grow tomatoes directly on soil, which may be contaminated from previous growing cycles.

3 RESULTS OF WU

3.1 Setting up disease test assay

Aiming to identify ToBRFV resistance in tomato wild relatives and to introgress them into tomato cultivars, WU has set up a disease assay at seedling stage to test tomato plants with ToBRFV (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Seeds germination and ToBRFV inoculation process

Infected plants were evaluated for presence or absence of symptoms (by visual score, Figure 2) and virus (by a quick test, Figure 3).

Figure 2. Four weeks post ToBRFV inoculation Moneymaker tomato plants. Symptoms inspection stage.

Figure 3. Rapid ToBRFV test for viral detection. ImmunoStrip® for Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), Agdia, Elkhart, U.S.A.

3.2 Natural resistance to ToBRFV found in two wild accessions

After screening about 60 accessions of 12 different *Solanum* species, two *S. pennellii* accessions have been identified resistant to ToBRFV (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Two *S. pennellii* accessions were scored asymptomatic and absent of ToBRFV.

3.3 Mapping and introgressing the resistance to tomato cultivars

Resistant plants of these two accessions were crossed with susceptible plants of tomato cultivar MoneyMaker to generate mapping populations and also for introgression of the resistance.

- For accession 1, F1 were obtained and F2 will be produced for mapping the resistance gene(s).
- For accession 2, F2 population was generated and tested with ToBRFV. Visual scoring for symptoms showed that the resistance segregates in the F2 population (Figure 5). Further mapping study will be performed to identify molecular makers linked with the resistance.
- For both accessions, backcrosses will be performed to introgress the resistance to cultivated tomato MoneyMaker.

Figure 5. Resistance to ToBRFV segregates in the F2 population of a crosse of Monemaker x *Solanum pennellii* accession 2.

In order to find ToBRFV-resistant rootstocks to prevent root mediated plant infections with ToBRFV, in VC we have screened 142 tomato plant accessions provided by Prof. Dani Zamir and NewBreed LTD. We have found three accessions belonging to *S. pennelli* and *S. lycopersicum* plants that served as ToBRFV resistant rootstocks for *Tm-2²* resistant scions.

Figure 6. Illustration of the conducted screening experiment for identification of resistant rootstocks.

- ToBRFV-resistant rootstocks were successful in protecting the susceptible scion from root inoculation but failed to protect the grafted plants from foliar inoculation.
- Therefore, the ultimate protection will be achieved when both scions and rootstocks are ToBRFV resistant.